

HYDROSEPHALIA: IN CHILDREN AND ADULTS - SYMPTOMS, CAUSES

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Abstract: *Hydrocephalus (Greek: ὕδωρ - - from the word "water" + κεφαλή "head") is a disease characterized by the accumulation of excess spinal fluid in the ventricular system of the brain, which is caused by the secretion of spinal fluid. (cerebral ventricles) Difficulty in reaching the site of absorption (subarachnoid space) into the blood system - occlusive hydrocephalus, or absorption disorder - occurs as a result of areorptive hydrocephalus.*

Hydrocephalus is a person who suffers from hydrocephalus.

Spinal fluid is also called cerebrospinal fluid, which is vital for nerve tissue function. The cerebrospinal fluid is present in both the brain and the spinal cord. In the brain, this fluid is stored in four ventricles in the center of the skull. The two upper ventricles are located in the two hemispheres, and the two lower ventricles are located along the central axis of the brain. The ventricles communicate with each other through a system of tubes called the waterways. In addition, cerebrospinal fluid can travel to the subarachnoid space that separates the cerebral cortex and to the cerebral cisterns at the base of the skull.

The functions of cerebrospinal fluid are different:

Protection of nerve tissues from external mechanical influences;

Removal of harmful substances from the brain and delivery of nutrients;

Maintain a stable value of intracranial (intracranial) pressure.

The volume of cerebrospinal fluid is relatively small, about 50 ml in infants and 120-150 ml in adults.

The cerebrospinal fluid, like blood, circulates in the cranial cavity. However, its composition is constantly changing: 3 times a day in adults, often in infants - 8 times a day. Adults produce 0.35 ml of cerebrospinal fluid per minute, about 500 ml per day. In adults, cerebrospinal fluid pressure can vary over a wide range - from 70 to 180 mm Hg. up to.

The cerebrospinal fluid is mainly formed in the ventricles of the brain. Two-thirds of the fluid is formed in the ventricular junction, and the rest in the ventricular

membrane and cerebral cortex. Inside the skull, in a special vein at the top of the neck, the venous sinuses absorb it.

TYPES OF HYDROSEPHALIA

There are three main forms of the disease: open, closed (occlusion), and hypersecretory.

The closed form of the disease develops when there is a physical barrier that prevents the re-flow of cerebrospinal fluid into the systemic bloodstream from the intended pathways of the skull. The cause of this type of disease can be various cysts, tumors or hemorrhages.

The overt form of hydrocephalus is observed when the mechanism of absorption of cerebrospinal fluid into the systemic bloodstream is disrupted. The cause of this type of disease is usually a previous infection, such as meningitis or the presence of blood in the subarachnoid space.

Hypersecretory hydrocephalus is a relatively rare disease that occurs in about 5% of cases. This occurs as a result of overproduction of spinal fluid. This condition can occur, for example, due to vascular pathology.

There are also congenital, acquired, and substitutable types of hydrocephalus. Congenital hydrocephalus is when a person has the disease from birth. Acquired hydrocephalus is a consequence of the diseases experienced. Substitute disease occurs when the brain tissue is degraded and replaced by an increased volume of cerebrospinal fluid.

According to the intensity of pathological processes, the disease is divided into acute and chronic types. The acute type develops within a few days, usually in a closed form, and requires immediate surgical intervention. The chronic type develops within a few months. It is often associated with an overt disease.

Depending on the location of the increase in cerebrospinal fluid volume, the disease is divided into external, internal and mixed types:

Externally, excess fluid accumulates mainly in the space between the cerebral cortex.

Internally, the disease affects the ventricles of the brain. This condition is often associated with a congenital closed form. In addition, internal hydrocephalus can be divided into symmetric and unilateral. Unilateral type of hydrocephalus is diagnosed when an increase in cerebrospinal fluid volume affects only one of the two symmetrically located ventricles.

In the mixed type, an increase in fluid volume is observed in both the ventricles and the space between the cerebral cortex.

In addition, the disease can have compensated and decompensated forms. In the compensated form, despite the increase in fluid volume, compression of the nervous structures of the brain is not observed and, accordingly, there are no negative

neurological symptoms. However, treatment of the disease if not started, it may progress to a decompensated phase.

According to the dynamics of development, hydrocephalus is divided into progressive, stabilized (stabilized) and regressive forms. Depending on the level of spinal fluid pressure, the disease is divided into hypertensive (high pressure), normotensive (normal pressure) and hypotensive (low pressure).

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